

Response to Aztec Labs RfC

Aztec Sequencer Selection and Prover Coordination Protocols

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I. Executive Summary

This response to Aztec Labs' Request for Comments (RfC) is the result of an ongoing research collaboration between Aztec Labs and BlockScience (*full disclosure: BlockScience is contracted by Aztec Labs for research, including the provision of this response*). Other work artifacts resulting from this collaboration are a report on aiding the decision for a Sequencer Selection protocol, as well as an ongoing simulation effort aimed at aiding risk management decisions and mechanism design of an economically sustainable Aztec infrastructure.

Through the selection of Fernet and Sidecar, Aztec Labs has decided upon a workflow for block production. Our response focuses on identifying whether this workflow appears to fulfill previously-defined requirements, while also providing additional views on potential risks that might become relevant for future risk management.

We note that an absence of any subsequently-identified risk from this response likely results from time and scope limitations in the analysis, rather than the response pointing toward the identification of a "perfect workflow". Risks are present in any economic infrastructure, whether they have been identified for risk management or not.

Our conclusion is that the proposed workflow generally addresses the prespecified requirements, allowing entities to permissionlessly participate in the building process to produce Layer 2 (L2) blocks.

We identify potential factors that might contribute to a centralization of the Sequencer and Prover roles, such as increasing returns to scale, early incumbency, and opportunity cost structures. Much of the centralization tendency of the builder process rests upon the potential of the process to support conditions under which a 'natural monopoly' can emerge, driving vertical integration of the Sequencer and Prover roles.

Additionally, we provide a loose classification of types of censorship, and highlight factors that could contribute to each type (as well as potential factors influencing censorship risk management). In particular, we note the possibility that adopting "based sequencing" for the fallback 'race mode' can potentially augment the risk of censorship (e.g. from L1 builders). The main driver of this observation is the potential market power of an L1 builder that could profit from inducing race mode with based sequencing (it should be noted that this is not a reflection of the utility of based sequencing as a protocol design choice).

Finally, we comment on our observations with respect to liveness and failure modes.

Fernet-Sidecar enables reliable block production in the Aztec network through a cascade of modalities. This cascade is presented as a state machine with parameterized, realtime state transition triggers. Both fixed block intervals and variable block intervals are discussed as simple changes to the state transition logic. While trigger parameterization provides a means of governing Aztec block production, determining appropriate values for the parameters will require computational simulations.

II. Overview

This response is divided into four sections, each loosely covering a (non-exclusive) subset of the requirements of Fernet-Sidecar. These sections and the relevant end-to-end building requirements are:

1. **Decentralization:** this section provides a perspective on how to evaluate the impact of centralization on participation in the builder process, focusing primarily upon identification of any factors which might contribute to centralization/vertical integration of the sequencer and/or prover roles (such as barriers to competitive entry and increasing returns to scale).
 - Associated Requirements:
 - Compatibility between the Fernet 14 sequencer selection protocol and Sidecar
 - Provision for permissionless participation
 - Ability to verify the entity generating a proof
 - Clearly articulated incentives for participants
 - Ability for sequencers to produce proofs by means other than engaging directly in a prover market (Sidecar)
2. **Censorship:** a loose classification of censorship types is defined, to assist in the assessment of tendencies toward centralization from a market power perspective, and in the risk management of censorship and its associated costs.
 - Associated Requirements:
 - Provision for permissionless participation
 - Privacy for participants in the proving protocol
 - Definition of the entity submitting completed work to L1
 - Clearly articulated incentives for participants
 - Ability for sequencers to produce proofs by means other than engaging directly in a prover market (Sidecar)
3. **Liveness:** Fernet-Sidecar protocol is considered as a state machine with realtime state transition events. In this way, the protocol is related to recovery, resilience, and adaptability required for reliable, on-going block production in the Aztec network.
 - Associated Requirements:
 - Graceful recovery in the event of an interruption/fault
 - Graceful reorg resilience
 - Scaling with available computing power
4. **Futureproofing:** Discussion of futureproofing is distributed throughout the liveness theme. Sidecar itself provides flexibility through an unpermissioned pool of Provers. Prover Selection is decoupled from cryptography implementation allowing to take future cryptographic improvements and challenges into account. Protocol parameters are listed with regards to state transition events.
 - Associated Requirements:
 - Flexible for future cryptography improvements
 - Clearly articulated protocol parameters

III. Themes

A. Decentralization

One may frame the ‘danger’ of centralization within the context of competitiveness between participants. When there are relatively few participants that can profitably enter a market there is monopolistic or oligopolistic competition or monopoly, and a driving goal of decentralization is to ensure both free access to and ‘fair play’ within such a competitive environment.

In a market with few firms the main threat to competitiveness is *incumbent centralization*, i.e. the tendency for an early participant in an ecosystem to understand and develop a profit-maximizing vertical structure that:

1. Provides *returns to scale* by internalizing costs and reducing entity-to-entity frictions, and
2. Leverages their *early incumbency* to deter potential competitors from entering the market.

While each of these characteristics alone may be sufficient to create a centralized market (this can be e.g. passing from monopolistic competition to oligopoly, and ultimately to monopoly) both are typically exploited by a participant to attempt to control as much of the entire revenue stream as possible.

Returns to Scale

Scaling here is best interpreted as a *technological constraint*—a participant considers whether or not it is possible to leverage e.g. infrastructure, business practices, funding sources etc. to achieve a centralized, or *vertical*, ‘stack’ of service provision that captures the end-to-end development of a product. In the Fernet-Sidecar implementation, identification of the technological constraints will determine the extent to which vertical integration is possible. Examples include:

- The substitutability of infrastructure used for sequencing in the proving process (high substitutability drives down the hardware costs of vertical integration);
- The ‘complexity’ costs of replicating a sequencer or prover role (lower costs make ‘sybilization’ of the sequencer and/or prover markets more likely to generate expected revenue increases that more than offset the increased costs above managing a single entity);
- The race-mode-specific infrastructure costs (a sequencer could strategically influence events to result in the failure to provide a proving commitment bond, or fail themselves to reveal their proposed block content, in order to then win the ‘first past the post’ proof race that follows).

A full analysis of the viability of these strategies requires an understanding of the cost side of the sequencer and prover entities, as well as any mitigation strategies to disincentivize sybilization and the commencement of race mode.

Early Incumbency

Vertical integration allows one internal business unit to absorb losses from another business unit, provided that future gains made possible with these losses are high enough. This can be leveraged to reduce the profitability of a potential competitor, deterring them from attempting to become part of the building process. A classical

example is of an incumbent, such as a chip manufacturing company, ‘dumping’ high output at low prices to drive out rivals and deter potential entrants (who may have cost constraints that cannot be satisfied at low prices), and then recouping more than the associated losses by acting as a monopolist thereafter, restricting output and increasing prices. The Fernet-Sidecar implementation may favor early incumbents because of:

- The implementation and ‘fine-tuning’ advantages that an incumbent garners from a longer presence in the building process, and
- The advantages of a sequencer potentially developing and leading a prover market, initially offering below-cost proving that deters other provers from entering the market.

The latter case most closely represents the classical incumbent example described, as developing a prover market may incur losses on the prover side that the sequencer side initially absorbs. These losses are then expected to be more than offset by the long-run prover market monopoly. (For an analysis of such ‘predatory pricing’ strategies and algorithms see e.g. Leslie, C. R. [2023], “*Predatory Pricing Algorithms*”, New York University Law Review v. 98 no. 1.)

Mitigation

One typical strategy to mitigate the potential benefit of centralization is to enforce—or generate market conditions which enforce—pricing such that ‘normal’ economic profit is attained, up to what is required for the market to generate its output (in this case, the composite good ‘ordered transactions / proven transactions’). Enforcement is typically itself centralized (such as regulating a natural monopoly by requiring average-cost pricing), but market conditions may exist which ‘self-enforce’ (such as contestable markets). It will be necessary to understand the cost structure of a vertically integrated sequencer, in particular its degree of increasing returns to scale, in order to assess if one or the other enforcement modality is ultimately feasible.

Teasing out the particulars of this cost structure will require an examination of the cost structure of a participant:

- Adopting the role of a sequencer and a prover;
- Adopting the role of an L1 participant (builder/validator) and an L2 participant (sequencer/prover).

If one or more of these cases implies increasing returns to scale from vertical integration, decentralization may be unstable as larger entities are formed by adopting multiple roles. The same conclusion also obtains if one or more of these cases implies that end-to-end proving is a *natural monopoly*, i.e. that the cost of proving is lowest when performed by a single vertically-integrated entity. This would act both as a deterrent to entry by other potential provers, and also capture the demand for proving services in the market. It is worth noting that these two situations are often identical, when the natural monopoly is driven by large initial infrastructure costs or high barriers to entry, as this can imply (at least weakly) increasing returns to scale. (For an insightful textbook treatment of returns to scale and natural monopoly, see e.g. Tirole, J. [1988], *The Theory of Industrial Organization*, MIT Press.)

Centralization and Opportunity Costs

Is centralization a ‘bad thing’ for the ecosystem? Because centralization may prevent participants from meaningfully engaging in the block building process, it can be considered as antithetical to the motivation of creating the Fernet-Sidecar permissionless workflow. Against this consideration would have to be weighed the following:

1. The ability of the workflow to allow multiple, decentralized, distinct (not ‘sybilized’) participants to earn an excess of revenue over cost (economic profit) that is at least as good as the next best available activity given their resources (*builder opportunity cost*);
2. The ability of the workflow to provide sufficient quality of service (timeliness, cost) to users of the network that they prefer a decentralized Aztec over the next best available ecosystem to process their transactions (*user opportunity cost*).

Note that as users may not necessarily care about the centralization of the network, the user opportunity cost will at least implicitly include the perceived quality of service from an alternative Aztec topology, such as a centralized service, even if such a service is not immediately available. This is because builder participants will likely recognize that this signals an opportunity for centralization if this results in an increased quality of service for the user.

Further understanding of these opportunity costs will likely suggest possible mechanisms that can be adopted to

- Maintain a required quality of service that exceeds that required due to user opportunity cost;
- Provide a minimum reward in a decentralized ecosystem that exceeds that required due to builder opportunity cost; and
- Dissuade any tendency to centralization from e.g. increasing returns to scale and/or a natural monopoly tendency, as described above.

Current mitigations already implemented into Fernet-Sidecar, such as builder staking and slashing, may or may not be sufficient once these opportunity costs have been understood.

B. Censorship

In general, censoring transactions is undertaken by a builder role (sequencer or prover) under one of three circumstances:

1. There is a monetary gain from censoring, i.e. censorship is *financially incentivized*; or
2. There is a non-monetary gain from censoring, i.e. censorship is *ideologically incentivized*; or
3. There is no gain from censorship but it occurs, i.e. censorship is *unintentional*.

These circumstances cannot be perfectly identified by an observer of a builder who—*ex post*—is seen to have engaged in censorship, although there exist strategies for probabilistically detecting or classifying censorship circumstances.

Given this, it is usually more fruitful to assess:

1. The *likelihood* of incentivized censorship, with an eye toward features of the builder workflow that reduce this likelihood, while understanding
2. The *rate* of unintentional censorship that may be considered ‘natural’ for the builder workflow under consideration, in order to provide a workflow that is resilient to censorship disruptions.

Financially Incentivized Censorship

Sequencer:

Although a sequencer is perhaps less incentivized to censor individual transactions (since transactions with private function calls prevent introspection for e.g. MEV opportunities), there is still a preference ordering that is induced by transactions according to the results of an optimization across fees (e.g. ‘MEV-boost’-ing). This is designed to reveal the willingness to pay for Aztec services (as is usual for auction-style resource allocation mechanisms), but does mean that resource-constrained users may find their *de facto* access to proposed blocks restricted. Since this possibility is present in nearly all such protocol systems it is difficult to see what, if any, mitigation strategies are available, or if any should be investigated (as doing so would destroy a large part of the incentive for a sequencer to participate).

In a sense, Fernet is already well-suited to place this type of censorship at or near the lower bound for an L2-rollup-to-L1 paradigm: all of the economic motivation rests at the L1 cost level, and intra-transaction information is not available to exploit by Aztec’s own design. Thus, if the role of a participant is limited to that of the L2 sequencer, then censorship risk at the individual transaction level is relatively low.

Sequencer as L1 Builder

The next aggregation layer above individual transactions is to treat the proposed L2 block itself as an object of censorship, and here the risk is more prevalent due to the timing/timeout structure of the Fernet-Sidecar implementation. The idea is that a sequencer is also an L1 Builder that is large enough to command a significant share of L1 block production. Given the economies of scale for L1 services, an L1 Builder may also be incentivized to participate as one or more sequencers. When ‘their’ sequencer role has the highest ranking proposal, the L1 Builder may be responsible for its inclusion in the L1 contracts, and the proposal is submitted as intended. But when another sequencer has the highest ranking proposal, the L1 Builder ‘holds up’ the L1 submission until the backup ‘race mode’ is triggered. At this stage the L1 Builder can submit their own original proposal permissionlessly, with the result that (depending upon the market power of the L1 Builder in the L1 space) a large fraction of sequencer proposals that arrive on L1 are built by the L1 Builder.

Much of the above argument rests upon

1. The market power of the L1 builder, i.e. the degree to which they can control L1 block production; and
2. The structure of ‘race mode’.

Market power occurs because an L1 builder can act as a ‘bottleneck’ to L2 rollup inclusion even under normal operating circumstances, and this can be exploited to *threaten* L2 block censorship and a concomitant default to race mode. Provided that the structure of race mode admits circumstances where the L1 builder could earn a

return (by e.g. submitting their own ‘ready-to-go’ block), this threat can be credible, and a sequencer who is not the same entity as the L1 builder may agree to a side payment to prevent the threat from being carried out. In this fashion an L1 builder and a separate sequencer may end up behaving “as if” they are a single entity.

Race mode structure has an impact because of the ease (or difficulty) of an L1 builder generating revenue if a threat is carried out. To the extent that the current version of race mode, utilizing a form of “based sequencing” (cf. e.g. J. Drake’s proposal at ETH Research) allows an L1 builder to submit a block permissionlessly, such a credible threat mechanism may be profitable at “relatively” low levels of market power on the part of the L1 builder. (This is reminiscent of bargaining games, cf. e.g. Myerson, R. B. [1997], *Game Theory: Analysis of Conflict*, Harvard UP for an introduction.)

Sequencer as Prover

On a smaller scale there may be a similar danger with a prover market dominated by a single large entity (“Prover”) who also acts as one or more sequencers. When their sequencer has the highest ranking proposal, they can be ‘selected’ by the sequencer (i.e. by the Prover itself) to prove the proposal, garnering the associated returns. When another sequencer has the highest ranking proposal, it may be that only the Prover is available in the prover market, who charges a high price for proving (higher than they charge themselves as sequencers). This price would be just under the reward that a sequencer would earn by proving the proposal themselves, providing the weakest incentive possible for the unfortunate sequencer to use the Prover.

Thus, the proving market microstructure can be a critical component of the capacity of a prover to censor sequencer blocks due to monopoly power (see ‘Decentralization’ above). If possible one would prefer a prover market that is naturally decentralized (e.g. with constant returns to scale production) and low entry costs. It is important to note that this depends upon the technology for proving—if it should be the case that the most natural market structure is monopoly, then one might entertain possible mitigations such as a protocol tax of the ‘winning’ prover, to drive profits down to what would be obtained in a decentralized equilibrium.

Ideologically Incentivized Censorship

One may imagine circumstances under which a series of transactions, or a proposed block of transactions, is censored for reasons other than financial gain. For example, it may be that an entity providing transactions is, for one or another reason, subject to external scrutiny that can render participants within the builder workflow liable for providing services to that entity. Another example is ‘for the LOLs’, i.e. behavior antithetical to the spirit and purpose of the ecosystem that does not confer a benefit (and may even be costly to execute).

Ideologically incentivized censorship occupies a middle ground between financially incentivized and unintentional censorship. On the one hand, it is hoped that the ecosystem is resilient to unintended ‘shocks’ (as discussed further below), and so to a certain extent censorship ‘for the LOLs’ can be treated as unintentional censorship. On the other hand, it is not difficult to see censoring an entity due to potential legal repercussions as ultimately a financial incentive (especially viewed as an opportunity cost), albeit several steps removed (e.g. legal consequences resulting in new costs, reduced profits, possible exit etc.). In the latter case, then, ideologically incentivized censorship may not be *first order* financially incentivized, but may be so to *higher*

order.

Risk Management

Fernet-Sidecar’s resilience to ideologically incentivized censorship relies upon the characteristics—including trigger events—of the backup ‘race mode’. This is discussed further below in the context of unintentional censorship. Similarly, ideologically incentivized censorship that is (say) up to second-order financially incentivized may be treated from the same point of view as that above for first-order financially incentivized censorship. The middle ground, where censorship is not taken for direct financial gain but possibly for indirect gains (or insurance) ‘down the road’ can be determined by the *risk management profile* that transactions handled by Aztec provides.

For example, it may be possible to partition transactions into distributions by visible attribute (e.g. by entity, size, frequency etc.). If this is the case, then a statistic may be generated that can be referenced per sequencer to assess if one or another attribute is probabilistically being censored, and to design a punishment strategy (such as stake slashing) that uses this statistic to deter, in expectation, attribute-based censorship. While this approach sacrifices *determinism*, it provides Aztec itself with the power to use its protocol incentive mechanisms to approach the problem of censorship from a risk management perspective, leveraging population (statistical) approaches that can be drawn from traditional risk management practice (cf. e.g. McNeil, A. J. [2015], *Quantitative Risk Management: Concepts, Techniques and Tools*, Princeton UP).

Unintentional Censorship

Censorship that occurs without a manifestation of participant ‘will’ (or, in the loosest sense, a will driven by random, exogenous factors) are considered unintentional, and may be treated as if they are ‘shocks’ to the builder process. Examples would include

- Completely unrationalizable but explicit transactions exclusion behavior (‘for the LOLs’);
- Infrastructure failures; and
- Low-probability clustering events, such as the happenstance that low gas fee transactions are correlated with one or more attributes of the transactions actor, so that *ex post* the appearance is that a type of actor has been censored.

The goal of the builder process in this context is *resilience*—unintentional censorship events should not persistently degrade the perceived performance of the network, by reducing trust in the sequencer’s proposal mechanism, transactions revelation flow, or prover proof submission sub-processes. To that end, such events should not

1. Be correlated across time or transactions attributes (which would indicate a *systemic* tendency toward censorship in particular contexts), so that the network is not confronted with repeated censorship events, leading to degraded performance;
2. Create cascade effects (externalities) where a single censorship event ‘snowballs’ into large-scale changes in transactions type or volume, again degrading performance;
3. Unduly penalize the builder (sequencer or prover) that has the unintentional censorship event attributed to their activity, so that participation in the builder process is not disincentivized from any penalties assessed due to censorship.

Shock resilience is a well-understood desired property of engineered systems, and many techniques relying upon e.g. signal processing can be fruitfully applied to a system to assess its resilience to disturbances such as unintentional censorship. The goal of such an analysis in the present context would be to minimize the risks of #1 - #3 above. For example, Aztec’s design goal of handling private function calls is potentially the most important mitigating factor as it removes the possibility of correlations between many transactions attributes that are hidden from the builder process, reducing the risk of #1 above.

Similarly, Fernet-Sidecar’s timing games for sequencer transactions revelation and prover proof submission are potential ‘levers’ that can be adjusted to minimize the possibility of cascade effects (#2 above). This is because such timing intervals provide ‘buffer periods’ where fluctuations can potentially be dampened, preventing amplification of an event over time. It can be a useful exercise in signal processing to posit particular shock functional forms, representing censorship events, and examining the impact of different timing intervals selected on the resulting risk of event propagation.

Finally, it should be noted that although slashing is a mechanism that can be used as a punishment strategy to ostensibly deter censorship, it should be assessed relative to the probability that censorship is unintentional, so that slashing does not become a disincentive to participation. This is a complex issue as censorship would not only have to be detected as an event, but its ‘type’ would need to be classified with a high degree of confidence prior to triggering a potential slashing event. Classification methods exist which are designed to help minimize making “Type I” or “Type II” probabilistic errors, although they cannot eliminate the risk (#3 above) entirely.

C. Liveness

To discuss liveness, Aztec can be seen as a state machine with some realtime aspects to state transition triggers. Aztec’s realtime clock is block production by its L1, the Ethereum network; so, this discussion of the realtime aspects of the triggering conditions will be in terms of Ethereum network block production rate. With this definition of liveness, any discussion of L1 liveness is out of scope.

Under the Fernet-Sidecar proposal pair for Sequencers and Provers, respectively, the sequence of state transitions required for a live Aztec network are shown by the “Aztec Network block production lifecycle” diagram in the RfC. These states are listed in the following table.

Table I: Fernet-Sidecar protocol states. Each protocol state is listed by unique name along with a brief description. State exit triggers are listed along with next state successful (*i.e.*, “*happy-path*”) and alternate transition modes. Triggers highlighted in square brackets are optional. These are discussed below under “Fixed vs. Variable Block Time”.

Ordinal	State Name	State Description	Transition Trigger	Success Modes	Alternante Modes
1	Proposal	Any Sequencer can propose a next block by posting a CtS ¹ to L1	Elapsion of n_1 L1 blocks [OR p_1 proposals posted]	At least one CtS is posted \rightarrow Proposal Selection	No CtS is posted \rightarrow Empty Mode
2	Proposal Selection	Proposal CtS Scores ² are evaluated. The Proposal with the highest CtS Score (b_s) is selected	Immediate	\rightarrow Prover Commitment	None
3	Prover Commitment	The Sequencer of b_s (s_s) chooses a Prover (p_s) who posts a CtP ³ to L1	Elapsion of n_3 L1 blocks [OR CtP posted]	CtP posted \rightarrow Reveal	CtP not posted \rightarrow Race Mode
4	Reveal	s_s posts the full contents of the b_s to L1	Elapsion of n_4 L1 blocks [OR Full b_s posted]	Full b_s posted \rightarrow Proving	Full b_s not posted \rightarrow Race Mode
5	Proving	p_s computes proof of b_s	Elapsion of n_5 L1 blocks [OR Proof of b_s posted]	\rightarrow Proof Submission	None
6	Proof Submission	p_s posts proof of b_s to L1	Immediate	Proof posted \rightarrow Finalized	Proof not posted \rightarrow Empty Mode

¹A CtS (Claim to Sequence) is a submission for a proposed next Aztec block that consists at least of the header of the proposed block and a random number generated by the Sequencer using a Verifiable Random Function (VRF).

²CtS Score is the result of a function that returns a unique ordinal based on a CtS.

³A CtP (Commitment to Prove) is a promise by a Prover to generate the necessary proofs for a Sequencer's proposed block. A CtP identifies the Prover and contains a signature from the sequencer and a posted bond that can be slashed if the proposed block is not finalized.

Ordinal	State Name	State Description	Transition Trigger	Success Modes	Alternante Modes
7	Race Mode	Anyone can post a block with proof to L1	First block posted	→ Finalize	None
8	Empty Mode	An empty block is posted to L1	Immediate	→ Finalize	None
9	Finalized	Vulnerability of proof tx to L1 reorg is reduced to an acceptable minimum	Posted Block and Proof reach threshold L1 block height (h_t)	→ Proposal	None

Under normal operation, aka “the happy path”, the Aztec network will transition through States 1-6 in order. At the end of State 6, both the full contents of a new Aztec network block and its proof will have been verified and successfully posted to the Ethereum blockchain. If any of the failure modes listed for States 1-6 occurs, then the happy path is exited by transition to either State 7, Race Mode, or State 8, Empty Mode. In Race Mode, anyone can submit a block/proof pair. In Empty Mode, the Aztec block slot is left empty. First valid pair received is posted to L1 as the next block.

As currently proposed, Race Mode only ends when a block and its proof are submitted to L1. Since the case of no block/proof pair being submitted cannot be ruled out, Race Mode would benefit from specification of a timeout trigger with a duration of n_7 . Should the Race Mode timeout expire, the pending Aztec block slot goes empty. If a timeout transition trigger is added to Race Mode, then the row for Ordinal 7 in Table I would change as follows:

- Transition Trigger would change to “Elapsion of n_7 L1 blocks [OR Full Block and Proof posted]”
- Success Mode would change to “Full Block and Proof posted → Finalize”
- Alternate Mode would change to “Full Block and Proof not posted → Empty Mode”.

Fixed vs. Variable Block Time

Table I lists default, time-based triggers for all persistent states. Timeout delay is parameterized using the symbol, n_i , where i is the state ordinal. Timeouts are in units of L1 blocks.

Optional, event-based triggers based on protocol participant behavior are shown in Table I (highlighted and in square brackets). The triggers shown are combined by a

simple OR gate. Such event-based triggers switch Aztec’s block building protocol from having fixed block time to having variable block time with the time-based triggers acting as timeouts and setting a maximum block time.

Technically, Aztec can be implemented in such a way that switching between fixed and variable block timing is isolated to specific code blocks for state transition triggers. Depending upon the expected rate of change or desired resistance to change of the triggering logic, changes can be governed as more static, hard-coded changes to the protocol, or they can be governed as more dynamic, configurational changes to the protocol’s trigger parameters. Potential transition trigger parameters for each state are listed in Table I. For a maximally dynamic system, transition trigger parameters could be adjusted algorithmically in response to:

- observed environmental factors such as
 - L1 gas fees,
 - time to last L1 missed slot,
 - L1 missed slot frequency,
 - L1 liveness (e.g. as defined here),
 - etc.
- and observed Aztec Network (L2) factors such as
 - L2 transaction volume,
 - time to last L2 race mode block,
 - L2 race mode block frequency,
 - time to last L2 empty block,
 - L2 empty block frequency,
 - etc.

Note that this list is not meant to be complete, but suggestive. Any such parameter should first be evaluated for satisfaction of requirements, system safety, and system goal trade-offs between it and other parameters, ideally using a simulation framework such as cadCAD (complex adaptive dynamics Computer-Aided Design).

However, such dynamism is ill advised as a first starting point. Understanding indicated by model simulations of parameter changes that reflects real network experience (and mitigation effects on potential risks identified in sections above) are a necessary precursor. Short of that, this level of dynamism adds complexity without an apparent purpose.

As mentioned in our prior report, because Aztec relies on its L1 network, Ethereum, as a source of truth to propagate state updates through the Aztec network, Aztec block production should operate synchronously with Ethereum. Fernet-Sidecar operates synchronously with Ethereum, and so the Ethereum network contains a sufficient log of Aztec block production for recovery from an Aztec Network interruption or fault assuming that copies of the local mempool are persisted.

Similarly, Aztec can operate with optimistic L1 reorg resilience by local rollback and replay of a single Aztec block assuming that copies of local private state are persisted. Pessimistic L1 reorg resilience can be achieved by updating Aztec network state with a lag of one Aztec block.

Sidecar enables scaling blocks to available compute by allowing Sequencers to negotiate deals with Prover networks. It must be noted, however, that a limiting resource for Aztec block production is likely to be available L1 blob storage (considering as of yet unclear blob market competition). Sidecar also incentivizes limiting block size

to available L1 blob storage as Provers risk having their proving bond slashed if L1 builders are unable (or unwilling) to fit the required transactions into L1 blocks.

Finally, Sidecar as a Prover Selection protocol provides ample flexibility for future cryptography improvements through non-enshrinement of any particular implementation. Instead, Provers would simply avoid posting a commitment to prove, if any such improvement rendered them unable to complete their job. This allows for flexibility within the Prover Pool, selecting only from those who feel both economically and technologically able to participate.

IV. Final Thoughts & Concluding Remarks

In this response we provide perspectives and identify features of the Fernet-Sidecar builder process that may be worth considering during the ongoing design and implementation iterations of the workflow. Some perspectives indicate that one or more features carry associated risks that can be mitigated through simulation efforts already in progress, while others might require ongoing monitoring and risk management efforts throughout the Aztec network lifecycle.

Overall, we see continuous progress on research and design efforts surrounding Sequencer and Prover coordination. The described workflow addresses its specified requirements and provides an important foundation for further research. Although such a novel design space naturally confers unique research, design and engineering challenges, addressing these challenges benefits both Aztec and the larger L2 community— some of these challenges are already enumerated towards the end of this request for comments. We enjoy the possibility to contribute and collaborate on many of these challenges where possible, and welcome any feedback to this (now extensive!) forum post.